

FROM NARRATIVES TO PATHWAYS

Participatory causal analysis in evaluating contributions to systems change in the context of Brazilian education
2025

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This case study tells the story of a collective evaluation and learning process that included five grantees (who we refer to as partners) of the philanthropic organization Imaginable Futures all working to advance equity in Brazilian formal and informal education systems. An adaptation of Outcome Harvesting (OH) (Wilson-Grau, 2018; Paz-Ybarnegaray and Douthwaite, 2017) was the overarching methodological approach chosen, with specific methods used in different moments of the journey, such as the COM-B model for understanding behaviour change (Mayne, 2019) and approaches to storytelling and listening (Burns, 2021; Sayem et al., 2022).

The facilitated process included participatory learning sessions and moments of discussion and sense-making among representatives of the five organizations, as well as tailored support from the evaluation team to each. Our methodological innovation sits at the intersection of exploring causal pathways in systems change

interventions and participatory evaluation, fields that are expanding and deepening to meet growing demands for meaningful evaluation. In this case study we reflect in particular on **how we supported meaningful and robust participatory causal analysis** within our methodological bricolage.

Forming the group and setting the basis for the collective journey

The education system today in Brazil is the result, among other factors, of the legacy of colonial and patriarchal systems that work against opportunities to include racially and otherwise excluded populations (Gomes, 2012; Gonçalves & Silva, 2000; Gonzalez, 1988). There is no simple 'fix' to this systemic problem and an appreciation of all the dynamics, from structural to relational within intersecting systems is required to make significant improvements for children throughout the country, especially for those historically left behind. As a result, a number of philanthropic funders, including [Imaginable Futures](#), are now exploring systemic approaches to achieving racial equity in education in Brazil (Imaginable Futures, 2024). But **how can they know if their funding is influencing systems dynamics in ways that contribute to greater equity?** Those reflections led the Imaginable Futures Brazil team to invite a group of their grantees to embark on a collective exploration of contributions to changing the dynamics of Brazil's formal and informal education systems towards more equity - see Table 1 to understand the group's composition.

Table 1 - Composition of the group**The five partners of Imaginable Futures**

Ensina Brasil: a non-profit organisation whose aim is to encourage diverse people capable of leading collective change in Brazilian education at all levels (<https://www.ensinabrasil.org.br/>).

IBEAC: a non-profit organisation that works to disseminate a culture of human rights through the transformation of people, communities and territories, strengthening participatory, creative and solidarity-based citizenship (<https://www.ibeac.org.br/>).

Cidade Escola Aprendiz: a Civil Society Organisation in the Public Interest (OSCIP) that contributes to the development of individuals and their communities by promoting experiences and public policies guided by an integral perspective of education (<https://www.cidadeescolaaprendiz.org.br/>).

Elos Institute: a social education organisation that strengthens people's ability to transform their reality through local community development, social mobilisation and leadership development actions (<https://institutoelos.org/>).

CEERT: non-profit organization that since 1990 defends the rights of the black population, in particular the youth and black women. It elaborates and implements programs to promote racial and gender equity in public and private institutions (<https://www.ceert.org.br/>).

The team of consultants supporting the journey was formed by an international researcher with expertise in participatory evaluation in different countries and contexts who led the process; a Brazilian consultant with experience in the field of education and racial equity, and a Brazilian consultant with experience in facilitating participatory processes in different contexts. Imaginable Future's learning partner, an international consultant with expertise in systems practice, was involved in the design of the journey, which started before the evaluation process we describe in this case study. The funder was also part of the core team, which allowed the facilitators to constantly check their position on possible changes in direction or emphasis and take into consideration their expectations as the process evolved. Imaginable Futures representatives and the facilitation team worked together to create the conditions so that the funder was also learning alongside the partners and themselves seen as a partner in this collective journey, without trying to camouflage the dynamics that are usually present in funder-grantee relationships.

What we describe is a story of three nested levels of evaluation and learning shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Levels of evaluation and actors participating in each

Nested levels of evaluation	Actors involved	How they engaged with the process
Collective evaluation about contributions to systems change	Imaginable Futures representatives and representatives of five partners	As a design and implementation team engaged in key decisions on collective purpose and learning across organisation specific findings on contributions to systems change.
Organizational evaluation about contribution to systems change	Representatives of each partner team (approx. 3 people per partner), including different levels in the organization's hierarchy	As part of the design and implementation team. Additional team members were involved in methodological choice, data collection, analysis and reporting. Leadership was engaged in key steps to support use of findings.
Evaluation of, with, by participants (leaders) supported by partners	Direct participants of organizational programmes identified as leaders; Other system actors	See table 3 for details of specifically who was involved by each organisation. The depth of engagement varies from participants as respondents, to participants as active agents in the evaluation process.

The collective journey we describe is one of intentional innovation, experimentation and learning by doing. Given the diversity of existing capacities and monitoring and evaluation (M&E) structures within each partner organization, the evaluation team provided bespoke support to each organization. This centered on nurturing capacities to monitor and evaluate programs with a learning-oriented approach, encouraging reflexivity and critical exploration of causal pathways, while also creating spaces for learning across teams.

Identifying the Focus of the Evaluation

The group's evaluation interests were explored collectively during the introductory cycle of online meetings between June and November 2022. The overall intention of this phase was to build trust between participants through exploring systems thinking and supporting conceptual alignment on systems change to inform the subsequent participatory evaluation phase. Broad interests towards a participatory evaluation effort were mapped in this phase. An in-person three-day workshop held in April 2023 launched the second phase. During the workshop, the facilitation team guided the mapping and prioritization of common interests to collectively define a macro evaluation question of interest to all partners. The overarching evaluation question that guided us in this journey is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Agree overarching evaluation question

Overarching question

How do our actions and methodologies contribute to the development of leaders who act for systemic changes that produce equity?

Subsequently, each organization defined the actors they would focus the exploration with and articulated their contextualized evaluation question, described in Table 3.

Table 3: Partners' evaluation focus

Overarching question: How do our actions and methodologies contribute to the development of leaders who act for systemic changes that produce equity?

IMAGINABLE FUTURE'S PARTNERS	KEY ACTORS (leaders acting for systems change)	CONTEXTUALIZED EVALUATION QUESTION
CEERT	Educators honored in an award on racial and gender equity practices in formal education	To understand the contributions of the Educate with Racial and Gender Equity Award (<i>Educar com Equidade Racial e de Gênero</i>) in the trajectory of educators who were awarded in the professional and school categories over the last 20 years, seeking to understand how this has influenced the work of these individuals in the construction of anti-racist educational practices and policies.
Cidade Escola Aprendiz	Council members of a program on Integral Education	To understand Aprendiz's contribution to the work of the Reference Center for Integral Education Councilors in promoting integral education policies throughout Brazil.
Ensina Brasil	Young graduates selected to work as teachers in public schools in three Brazilian municipalities and actors who interact with them (students, fellow teachers, school management and the municipality's education department).	To understand what changes the participants of the Ensina program bring to the school community during the two years of the program.
IBEAC	Women who work in a support program for mothers in the district of Parelheiros, in the southern zone of São Paulo, and other actors who interact with them (assisted mothers, children, community leaders)	To understand the contributions of the Center of Excellence in Early Childhood (<i>Centro de Excelência em Primeira Infância - CEPI</i>) to significant changes in the lives of the women who work in the Program and to the impact they have on the territory.
Instituto Elos	People who participated in a leadership development program in the Baixada Santista region (SP) between 2007 and 2023	To understand the contribution and impact of Elos, based on the Warriors Without Weapons Program (<i>Guerreiros Sem Armas</i>), on personal, collective and territorial transformations at the Baixada Santista.

Designing the evaluation

The evaluation design challenge we had to grapple with was born of the systemic and participatory intentions of this collaborative effort. On the one hand, we needed a design that would support the collective exploration of systems change across all organizations, in order to build a view of what the portfolio is achieving as a whole. On the other, we needed flexibility to work with each organization's own questions and context, to ensure ownership and use for all partners. Our response was to apply methodological bricolage, creating a patchwork of relevant tools for different phases of the evaluation in order to be 'fit for context' (Aston & Apgar, 2022).

We adapted Outcome Harvesting to provide a structured methodology that was then bricolaged to meet the needs of each organization's specific question and design. As a 'goal independent' approach, OH embraces complexity, starting from an observable change and tracing contribution backwards, rather than using predefined indicators of success that are articulated in linear theories of change. The approach aims to pick up on all forms of change, intended and unintended, positive and negative. We combined elements of Most Significant Change (MSC) (Davies & Dart, 2005) and life story processes (Hacker & Sharma, 2022; Sayem et al., 2022) to develop contextualized storytelling processes with each organisation. A summary of the stages of the collective evaluation is described below.

Main stages of the collective evaluation of contributions to systemic changes in Brazilian education towards greater equity

1. Setting up the group of partners, building bonds of trust, and creating alignment on core concepts (June to October 2022).
2. Mapping broad interests for a collective participatory evaluation of causal pathways (November 2022).
3. Defining the overarching questions for the evaluation and mapping the specific interests of each organization (April-May 2023).
4. Applying the COM-B model to understand the expected changes in the behaviour of the targeted leaders (June 2023).
5. Offering training in participatory evaluation methods, with a focus on the core Outcome Harvesting approach, and mentoring sessions to design each organization's story collection plans (June-August 2023).
6. All teams carry out the first round of collecting stories of significant change with the key actors defined by each (September-November 2023).
7. Story analysis meetings with each organization (mapping of causal pathways, identification of outcomes, creation of summary paragraphs by story, analysis by grouping stories with common characteristics) (October-December 2023).
8. In-person session to share the results to date; in-depth discussions on topics of common interest; cross-analysis of findings (December 2023).
9. Second round of data collection (substantiation and triangulation) and continuation of the analysis with each organization (January to March 2024).
10. Collective in-person session focused on cross-analysis among all organizations (June 2024).
11. Writing of individual reports by each organization and preparation of collective analysis documents on the process and results (April-October 2024).

Collecting Causal Stories

Uncovering and exploring the emergent causal pathways within each organization's evaluation process also required a combination of analytical approaches. To help build skills for critical examination of underlying (often hidden) assumptions, we first used, during the design phase, the COM-B model (Michie et al., 2011) of behaviour change as a heuristic to explore potential contextual conditions that influence if and how actors shift their behaviours. This helped to focus each evaluation design by narrowing down on which specific actors in the system to engage with, and to find a balance in the storytelling processes such that participants could share their experiences in ways that mattered to them, while also prompting for the broad areas of change the evaluations were interested in - *leaders acting for systems change*.

Each organization developed specific prompt questions to open up the storytelling process in ways that ensured it was not simply an exercise of collecting positive stories that were driven by a desire to confirm existing assumptions the organizations held.

Examples of prompt questions used by the teams:

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- *Looking back over the last X years (since the person took part in the Award), which have been the most significant changes in your pedagogical practice?*
 - *Please share a story of change in your work in integral education over the last ten years. Tell us more about it. What was it like before? What events contributed to this happening? What actions were implemented to bring about these changes?*
 - *Think back over the last few years as a mother/leader/Mobilizing Mother/child in this community, what have been the biggest changes you've experienced? Could you choose one that you think is important to you and tell me the story of how that change came about?*

The evaluation team shared guidelines for the story collection process while allowing a degree of openness for each team to collect the stories in forms that were in line with their ways of working, resourcing and capacities. This meant some applied open-ended and participatory forms of story collection and storytelling and listening, while others were more structured in their approach. For example, one organization used body-mapping (Skop, 2016) to capture experiences of change from children, others used interview based collection, and others used collective storytelling

workshops. The result was the collection of a range of stories in different formats. The attention to context specificity and the associated methodological flexibility is aligned with more inclusive forms of rigour (Apgar et al., 2024; Chambers, 2015) which are appropriate in conditions of complexity.

Analysis and Mapping of Causal Pathways

Analysis of narrative data collected through the stories was based on use of critical and in-depth causal analysis. This entailed breaking down the causal pathways as described in the stories and mapping the cause-effect relationships based solely on what was in the data. Each story was first transcribed, and then mapped as causal pathways using an online post-it board. Common color coding was used across all organizations to detail different types of causal factors, such as feelings (that might have motivated a particular action), changes in the external context (that help to explain a cause-effect relationship), influence on the behaviour of other actors (the outcomes related to influencing system actors).

Example of the causal pathways created by the organizations are shown in the figure below.

Summary paragraphs were written for each mapped story, making explicit the contextual background information, the information that answered the evaluation question and the contribution claims in relation to the Programme under analysis. Table 4 presents two examples of summary paragraphs.

Table 4 - Summarizing the collected narratives

Example 1: summary of the story of a participant in the Elos Institute programme.

GSA04 is a young black man from a humble and left-wing activist family who dedicates his life to the fight for social justice, especially the right to housing and to the city. He used to teach history in the state school system in Santos (SP) and actively participates in local social movements. With a strong network of connections, he is pushing for social change in his community, using tools learnt in immersions to strengthen his political actions. Prioritizing collective and decentralised decision-making processes, GSA04 recognises his role as a young leader, building on the achievements of previous generations.

GSA04 has seen his trajectory receive a significant boost from the programme. He developed greater self-confidence and discipline, as well as started to feel more determined and lighter on his journey, after interacting with people from different cultures and realities who shared common ideals. The GSA Network became his family, offering assistance wherever there was a participant in the programme.

In 2023, GSA04 was elected as a Guardianship Councillor in Santos and became a Councillor of the Municipal Council for Urban Development, continuing his fight for land regularization in the local neighborhood association. Contact with other GSA participants who shared his struggle renewed his energy and spurred him on with even more determination.

Example 2: summary of the story of a participant in the Ensina Brasil programme.

This is the story of an indigenous ENSINA who, before joining the Programme, faced a number of challenges, such as agrarian conflicts in her village and a strong context of social vulnerability. Her participation in the Programme was made possible by a grant from Ensina Brasil. The day before classes started, her house was flooded and she received help from the Ensina's network.

At school, she wore a headdress and body paintings of her people. The students got excited to meet her. She wondered about the lack of indigenous stories in the teaching materials. She then decided to start a project to re-educate the school community with a focus on combating stereotypes. In addition to teacher training and exchanges with students, she also revised the teaching materials. As a follow-up, she also tried to set up a reforestation project at the school, but faced lack of resources. So she thought of alternatives involving the students, who brought seeds from home and took care of the land themselves. The project was submitted to the Restore Nature Olympics and was selected among the finalists, thus attracting the attention of the Municipal Secretariat of Education. With those results achieved, with the support of the school management she created days of activities

exclusively dedicated to indigenous peoples at the school. She also reports that the students began to question eurocentric concepts, developed a critical eye to stereotypes, to the history of native peoples, and began to respect differences.

This ENSINA says that, as an indigenous woman, access to many sectors of society is difficult because of the lack of inclusion and institutional racism. Ensina Brasil has provided her this access, and this facilitates articulations within institutions with a focus on creating anti-racist policies. 'As an indigenous woman, it took me 37 years to get to a Department of Education to talk about anti-racist education. It was through Ensina that I was able to gain this access,' she says.

The summary paragraphs were grouped according to categories pre-established by the teams. These categories, or tags, either referred to identity or demographic information (e.g. racial ethnicity, year they've participated in the program, region, gender) or to analytical categories, such as the type of change reported or the level of change. In this second case, the names of the categories varied according to how the organization interpreted the reported changes, which could be related to previous formulations of its Theory of Change and M&E system. Table 5 presents the choices of analysis tags among the group.

Table 5 - Grouping the collected stories under analysis tags

Organization	Analysis tag 1	Analysis tag 2	Analysis tag 3	Analysis tag 4
CIDADE ESCOLA APRENDIZ	Racial-ethnic identity	Gender	Role in the educational system	Region
IBEAC	Racial-ethnic identity	Start date in the programme (3 or less years ago; more than 4 years ago)	Educational level	
ELOS INSTITUTE	Racial-ethnic identity	Gender	"Protagonism" level (according to the organization's conceptualization)	
CEERT	Award category (individual or school level)	Award's edition		
ENSINA BRASIL	Territory	Type of initiative	Level of change	Change in students

The intention of analysis through these sub-groupings was to identify similarities and differences in their stories that may relate to these predefined categories - to

'who' the leaders are, the timeframe of the change described and its relationship to the intervention. The systems change aspect of the causal analysis was then added through the use of a common systems change framework that focused on identifying influences on visible dynamics (rules and norms, information flows, power and decision-making, system goals, guiding beliefs and interdependencies) and hidden system dynamics (myths, metaphors and mental models) (Lynn, 2022).

Each partner produced an individual report of their evaluation findings, containing their analysis and response to their contextualised evaluation question. These findings were subsequently used to inform our collective evaluation about contributions to systems change. In the following section we share findings that resulted from looking across all five partner level evaluations with illustrative examples from each.

Collective-level findings

Analyzing the changes reported by the different leaders involved in the programs being evaluated by the partners, we found a first level of changes in the leaders themselves (individual level outcomes). These changes included:

- **Broadening their vision of the world and of themselves**, enabling these leaders to expand their sense of self-worth, to recognise injustices, break from previous prejudices, understand their rights more deeply and gain more self-esteem and self-respect. In many cases, these changes have affected their relationships with their family and friends.
- **Gaining a sense of belonging to a network of support** with people motivated by common goals, which, in several accounts, led to a greater sense of confidence to continue carrying out their work.
- **The continued professional and academic development of the person** involved in the programme, which has helped them to gain more recognition, achieve new opportunities and broaden the scope of their actions.

Overall, the leaders recognized that having first been through an internal process of change, contributed to broadening and deepening the impact of the actions they then were able to carry out in support of systems change. **The types of change generated by the work of these leaders and their contributions to changes in the dynamics of the system (system level outcomes) were grouped as follows**, and as exemplified by the following excerpts:

- Strengthening actions to promote equity in the contexts in which they engage (schools, childcare centres, universities, social movements), influencing visible power in those spaces and thus contributing to changing

rules and norms of the system. As a consequence, those actions tended to contribute to transforming **myths, metaphors and mental models.**

'At the first class council, we were more reserved, swallowing some things dry and with a lump in our throat, and then over time we gained space, the trust of the other teachers, of the coordination, of the school management and all the rest. And at the next class council (...) I already felt like a teacher at the school who had her voice and her space to speak, I said: 'I don't know if you know, but this student is going through this and this situation, he works, he already has an age-grade distortion, so the classes really aren't interesting for him' (...). We did this with several students, and this became the dynamic of the Class Council (...), talking about that student's life, what might be having an impact on the results they're getting in the classroom. That was the change in mentality that even reflected in the IDEB data afterwards, which was positively affected.' - Narrative from a young participant in the Ensina Brasil programme.

- Broadening the scope of their actions, becoming involved in training processes that promote equity in contexts they hadn't been previously engaged in, such as offering pedagogical support for schools; creating diverse training programmes, from nursery to postgraduate-level; reviewing teaching materials to make them more inclusive; working in community spaces such as health centres; resulting in new **information flows** in the systems.

'When George Floyd's murder happened, there started to be this movement of some people on social media inviting black personalities to manage their social media in order to have a wider reach of the debate and so on. I said I want to be part of this movement, I think I could invite a black intellectual to bring a discussion to Unicamp that we're not having. And certify the participants with the Unicamp Diploma. The pandemic allowed people to carry out virtual activities. (...) I invited Professor Sidnei Barreto Nogueira, author of the book Religious Intolerance. (...) He proposed that we also invited Professor Ellen de Sousa and we formed a postgraduate course called Epistemological Turn for an Anti-Racist Education (...). We only opened it up to postgraduates, so it wasn't a course that anyone could enrol in. We opened 200 places, 100 for Unicamp students and 100 for external students. Then there was a whole confrontation within the university about what the criteria were, colleagues questioning it, saying that it was absurd to have a course for so many people, that postgraduate studies are a space for dialogue in smaller groups, for in-depth exchange. (...) The university regulations didn't allow us to open more places for outside students than for inside students and even without knowing if we would have 100 internal students, we opened 100 internal places in order to open 100 external places. We had 1000

applications from postgraduate students from all over Brazil and abroad (...), students from Spain, Germany, Cape Verde, from all regions of Brazil, almost all Brazilian states. It was a struggle to select the 100 people who would be guaranteed a place, wasn't it? And so 1,000 people, postgraduate students from all over Brazil, wanted to discuss an epistemological turn towards anti-racist education. So it was very impactful. We did the course, it was a success. Then we published a book with the students' work, (...) with the support of the publisher Pedro João for this publication, it was a very nice piece of material that we put together.' - Person honoured by the CEERT Award

- Taking up positions that monitor the implementation of public policies such as, for example, working on the implementation of Brazilian legislation for education in ethnic-racial relations¹; working in or with municipal and state education departments; working in the Guardianship Council and in Municipal Health Councils; therefore acting on **power and decision-making** dynamics, influencing changes in **rules and norms** and in the **system's objectives**.

'Taking part in the Award was a very important recognition for my career. After the Award, I was able to make myself available to work in management, and the opportunity has opened up for me to work in the Directorate of Education of one of the regional offices of the Belo Horizonte Municipal Department of Education. I'm working as a pedagogical advisor on race relations, a position that is accompanying more than forty schools (...) in discriminatory situations, such as a teacher who has made a racist statement or a student who has assaulted another student. (...) Next year, in addition to the monitoring tool, we're going to build a tool to track the implementation of Law 10.639 for the region, in my case the Pampulha region.' - Narrative from a person honoured by the CEERT Award

- Establishment of new support networks between people who are active in processes aimed at reducing inequalities or strengthening pre-existing networks (study groups on education for ethnic-racial relations; women's support and empowerment networks), contributing to changes in the system's **information flows** and **mental models**.

'Today I was talking to the girls in the kitchen about how, when you enter the Centre of Excellence in Early Childhood, the first change comes with us as individuals, and then we realise that we've affected our children, our partners. Today I know how much the neighbourhood has changed and how rich it is in various things, projects, schools, now there are nurseries, EMEIs. And some

¹ Brazilian laws 10639/2003 and 11645/2008.

of these spaces are our partners, and we talk about the project, the importance of early childhood care, the importance of caring for women, caring for our team, the collective. And it's the collective of women strengthened by women, and they are individual stories, stories that touch us, stories that we see ourselves in, stories that we want to help in some way, and they are stories that we learn from.' - Narrative from a "Mobilizing Mother", a member of IBEAC's Early Childhood Centre of Excellence.

Uncovering the causal pathways

The partners' programmes that became the focus of each evaluation had different levels and types of previously defined Theories of Change. Those who had already articulated assumptions about the program's impact sought to understand whether the findings confirmed, extended or refuted previous theories, especially by identifying the contributions of external factors, unrelated to the organizations' explicit interventions, to the reported changes. Those who had intuitions about the impact of the programs but had not yet articulated them explicitly took advantage of the analysis to then inform new theories of change now based on their causal analysis. Overall, the process contributed to all having more systematic and rigorous evidence about immediate and indirect consequences of the analyzed programs. More often than not, the stories confirmed assumptions about the outcomes programmes contributed to, which was useful for the organisations given relative weaknesses in their ability to monitor contributions to systems change.

In all cases, what was particularly new and useful was better understanding the causal pathways that lead to different types and levels of outcomes. From the causal analysis, it was possible to understand not only what changes had occurred, but also how they had come about, and what contextual conditions explained where change had or had not happened. Insights emerged about aspects of change that had previously been somewhat hidden, or implicitly assumed but never explicitly investigated, for example: understanding that work to sustain active networks among the leaders was critical to supporting actions these participants were then able to carry out. In what follows, we share examples of the findings that shed light on specific contextual conditions that influenced the pathways of change for individuals within the system, and, show examples of contribution claims linking the evidenced outcomes to the interventions of the analysed programmes.

a) Contextual conditions influencing causal pathways

Students' life conditions and structural inequalities they face limited their hopes for the future: a student that had the opportunity to be taught by an Ensina teacher narrates that she had no hopes of going to university before

having contact with this Ensina teacher. She explains this was the result of the difficult conditions she had to face every day to continue going to school - living far away from school and going to integral education, requiring her to leave home early and return late, were two contextual factors she cited as reasons why she was thinking about stopping studying.

 Changes in rules due to shifting contextual conditions (driven by the covid-19 pandemic) created opportunity to develop new actions and/or broaden the impact of existing ones: the flexing of University rules towards online modules during the covid-19 pandemic, created the opportunity for a previously CEERT awarded teacher to invite external specialists to co-create a postgraduate module that was offered to 200 participants from all over Brazil and other countries. This successful and innovative experience led to the publication of a book featuring the students' work.

 Personal journey of being educated in an exclusionary model motivates teacher to become an integral education practitioner and activist: An advisor to the Cidade Escola Aprendiz Reference Centre for Integral Education reported that her involvement with the issue of integral education began after she was subjected to a banking, racist, centralising and Eurocentric model of education. As a reaction to these subjugating experiences, she was motivated to search for more humane ways of practising education in the classroom, which in turn led her to meet and get closer to the Reference Centre.

b) Contribution claims

Looking across all partners' findings we found the strongest evidence of **contribution** was linked to the following programme actions (strategies). Some contribution claims linked to more subtle aspects relating to 'how' they implemented the work, rather than the specific activities, resulting in more nuanced and expanded understand of how their ways of working contribute to achievement of system level outcomes in the longer term;

- Capacity building and expanding repertoires through the provision of training, pedagogical materials and personal development opportunities;
- Forming networks of support among leaders, contributing to mutual support and joint actions;
- Promoting greater visibility of the work carried out by the leaders through the creation of initiatives to share the work with broader audiences;
- Applying participatory methodologies that were often replicated by the leaders in the actions they implemented as a result of their involvement in the programmes.

The following image synthesizes the pattern in the causal pathway of change that was perceived among most stories collected by the five organizations.

Facilitation team's reflections on the process

Ensuring robust conceptualization while encouraging a plurality of world views

Generally, in evaluation, we are concerned with multiple forms of validity, indeed while simple models of validity are often presented as the “gold standard”, such as the Cambellian framework of statistical, internal, construct and external validity (Campbell & Stanley, 1963) in reality, there are over 40 different conceptualisation in use (Downes & Gullickson, 2022). Within all forms of validity, however, there is agreement that robust conceptualization supports greater rigour and so credibility of results. In our experience of this collaborative systems evaluation, however, there was a tension between building clarity on how we agreed on the ‘right’ conceptualization of systems dynamics and behaviour change amongst all partners, and staying true to a culturally-responsive approach which recognises plurality in worldviews and epistemologies, and so too in how we experience and make sense of the world.

What we aimed to find was a middle ground. Offering frameworks (such as the COMB model and the systems dynamics framework) into the collective dialogic space to help give sufficient structure and provide a center of gravity, while also creating space for partners to interpret and make sense in relationship to their own experiences and conceptualization. For some partners, this might have hit up against their own formulations of their organizational theories of change or ways of understanding systems change (as located in the realm of individual transformation versus the structural changes in a system) which likely was uncomfortable. Beyond any discomfort or confusion this might have created, there was also the need to manage the risk that the results might not end up being useful if they did not speak

to their own organizational strategies. What enabled us to continue on the journey and navigate some of these tensions and uncomfortable moments was the high level of trust and co-ownership that had been generated through the process.

Building co-ownership through reflexivity and appropriate structure

For the facilitation team, the experience of curating the safe space within which we could go deep and learn together was an ongoing challenge. Building co-ownership in any participatory process is not simply a box that is ticked at the outset, or through the use of one stand-alone tool, but rather, is an ongoing process that requires reflexivity (Scott-Villiers, 2022). This is perhaps one of the biggest challenges evaluators face in structures that value fidelity to prescribed methods over flexibility and methodological bricolage. In this case, the learning orientation and the power-awareness of the funder allowed for such reflexivity. Yet in spite of this space, how to practically remain open to move with the whole group, while working with a diverse set of organizations, with varying levels of comfort with flexibility or rigidity, is not straightforward. Given the contextualized approach taken by each partner to data collection, finding a common enough analytical strategy to be able to move together at a similar enough pace, and look across our findings was not easy. Our learning here is that at key moments of the process, the facilitators had to structure the process in ways that would support synthesis across, perhaps sacrificing some level of freedom and flexibility for partners. We did this practically through providing templates, a common approach to mapping causal pathways and formats for reporting.

Building trust through navigating power

One of our proudest process outcomes was the genuine atmosphere of trust that was established between organisations that don't normally come together to share their work, and in many cases are competing for increasingly limited funding for social change initiatives in Brazil. This, we feel, was one of the reasons partners experienced this collaborative evaluation process as unique compared to other evaluation journeys. Embarking on a different evaluation journey, one which is explicitly aiming to openly explore outcomes as they emerge, both positive and negative, requires questioning of one's assumptions (Bertermann & Martin, 2024). Such a process required partners to be humble, honest and vulnerable. It is unusual that this level of sharing occurs with a funder in the room, indeed, the marked power dynamics in most evaluation that is top-down and performance driven (Apgar & Allen, 2021; Roche & Kelly, 2012) tends to close down rather than open up conversations about what isn't working and how to do better together. At the same time, this was an opportunity to celebrate together what was being achieved, as the results show, all organizations were able to evidence some contributions into the system, building a space for each organization to be inspired by each other's work and begin to build collective power.

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